

EFFECT OF FIBER ORIENTATION AND LAMINATE THICKNESS ON THE
MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF PEEK/C.F. AND PPS/C.F.
AFTER IMPACT LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Effect of impact loading on the mechanical properties of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced Polyether Ether Ketone (PEEK) composite was studied. Laminates with fiber orientation of $[+45/O_2]_{2S}$ and $[O/+45/90/-45]_{2S}$ after impact loading also have been investigated. The damaged behavior was observed from optical microscopy and SEM. Result shows that the damaged area of $[+45/O_2]_{2S}$ is larger than that of $[O/+45/90/-45]_{2S}$. However, $[O/+45/90/-45]_{2S}$ shows more severe damage than that of $[+45/O_2]_{2S}$ due to 0° layer fiber breakage and matrix cracking. Furthermore, the retention of tensile and flexural strength of $[O/+45/90/-45]_{2S}$ decreases more prominently than that of $[+45/O_2]_{2S}$. Damaged area of $[O_2/+45_2/90_2/+45]_S$ (2.5 mm) is smaller and mechanical properties retention is better than that of $[O_2/+45/90_2/+45]_S$ (2.0 mm).

Key words: Instrumented falling weight impact , PEEK/C.F. , PPS/C.F. composite , property retention , damaged

behavior, fiber orientation, effect of thickness.

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to save fuel and to increase the speed of aircraft, weight reduction of aircraft and aerospace structures is the major concern to design engineer. Hence, the use of carbon/epoxy composites with high specific modulus and strength has been increased substantially. However, carbon/epoxy composites show inherent poor resistance to impact due to its brittle matrix (1-4). Fiber breakage, matrix cracking and delamination occurred in composites under impact loading (1) and mechanical properties reduced. Consequently, tougher thermoplastic resins were developed as matrices for continuous fiber reinforced composites. The thermoplastic resins for high performance composites including semicrystalline thermoplastic polymers such as polyether ether ketone (PEEK), polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) were developed recently (2). In this study, composites of different fiber orientations, $[+45/0]_{2S}$ and $[0/+45/90/-45]_{2S}$ were studied under impact loading. Mechanical properties of the composites were investigated when they suffered impact damage (5-8).

II. EXPERIMENTAL

II.1. Materials and Specimens

A 0.075mm (3mils) thick PEEK film and a 0.125 mm (5 mils) thick carbon fiber reinforced PEEK prepreg tape APC-2 used in this study were supplied by the Imperial Chemical Industries, U.K. A 0.075mm (3 mils) thick PPS film and a carbon fiber reinforced PPS prepreg were commercial products under the trade name Ryton^R Poly(phenylene sulfide) and AC40-60, respectively, from the Phillips Petroleum Company, Bartlesville, Oklahoma, U.S.A. The carbon fiber woven cloth (3k), #3101 with a weight of 200g/m², is a product of the Toho company, Japan.

The test specimens were compression molded with a picture frame mold by interlaying film and carbon fiber

cloth. Samples were preheated at 316°C (PPS) or 390°C (PEEK) for 20 minutes, then were molded at 200 psi for 20 minutes followed by transferring it to a cold press. APC-2 and AC40-60 were processed by compression molding with the processing conditions recommended by the manufacturers.

II.2. Impact Test and Photomicrography

Impact tests were performed in an instrumented falling weight impact tester. The impact tap is 1.27 cm in diameter with a hardened steel hemispherical head as described in ASTM-3029 Type B. The striker has a total weight of 4.865 kg. The impact energies were controlled by adjusting the height of the striker. The specimens were removed from the supporter after impact, optical microscopy and SEM were then utilized to determine the extent of the internal damages (delamination) and external damages of the specimen. In addition, photomicrographs were taken to examine the damaged phenomenon.

II.3. Mechanical Properties

Flexural and tensile strength tests were conducted with an Instron testing machine Model 1123, Instron Co., U.S.A. Specimen dimensions and test procedures were followed the specification of ASTM D-790 and ASTM D-3039, respectively.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

III.1. Damage Phenomenon

A. Photomicrography

(a) Effect of fiber orientation

Effect of fiber orientation on the impact damaged APC-2 (PEEK/C.F.) was studied when the composites was laminated with two different fiber orientations, i.e. $[+45/0_2]_{2S}$ and $[0/+45/90/-45]_{2S}$ (quasi-isotropic) PEEK/C.F.

From the observation of optical microscopy of the cross-section of specimens, impact damage shows a significant

effect on the composites. Figures 1a and 2a are the optical micrographs (50X) of virgin $[\pm 45/0_2]_{2S}$ and $[0/+45/90/-45]_{2S}$ PEEK/C F. Figure 1b shows $[\pm 45/0_2]_{2S}$ suffered 4.29 J (38.4 in-lb) impact energy, fiber breakage on 45° layers and matrix cracking can be found on the rear face of impacted region. Figure 2b shows fiber breakage on 0° layers, matrix cracking on 45° and 90° layers existed in impact damaged $[0/+45/90/-45]_{2S}$ specimen. As shown in Figure 1c when impact energy increased to 8.58 J (76.8 in-lb), $[\pm 45/0_2]_{2S}$ shows partial fiber breakage on 0° layers, consequently, more severe damage occurred than suffered 4.29 J energy. Figure 2c shows the damage of $[0/+45/90/-45]_{2S}$ which exhibits fiber breakage on two 0° layers and more matrix cracking at the same impact energy. Figures 1d and 2d show that severe fiber breakage and matrix cracking in both composites with 12.87 J (115.2 in-lb) impact energy.

(b) Effect of composite thickness

Effect of thickness on the impact damaged APC-2 (PEEK/C.F.) was studied when the composites were laminated with the orientations of $[0_2/\pm 45/90_2/\pm 45]_S$ (2.0 mm) and $[0_2/\pm 45_2/90_2/\pm 45]_S$ (2.5 mm) PEEK/C.F.

From the optical microscopy observation of the cross-section of virgin $[0_2/\pm 45/90_2/\pm 45]_S$ (2.0 mm) and $[0_2/\pm 45_2/90_2/\pm 45]_S$ (2.5 mm) as shown on Figures 3a and 4a. Figures 3b and 4b show that matrix cracking and delamination occurred in $[0_2/\pm 45/90_2/\pm 45]_S$ (2.0 mm) and $[0_2/\pm 45_2/90_2/\pm 45]_S$ (2.5 mm) when they suffered 4.29 J impact energy. $[0_2/\pm 45/90_2/\pm 45]_S$ (2.0 mm) shows more severe delamination and matrix cracking than that of $[0_2/\pm 45_2/90_2/\pm 45]_S$ (2.5 mm).

As indicated in Figures 3c and 4c, when impacted energy increased to 8.58 J, the 0° layers on rear face of $[0_2/\pm 45/90_2/\pm 45]_S$ (2.0 mm) exhibited very severe fiber breakage, but only partial 0° layer fiber breakage and matrix cracking occurred on rear face of $[0_2/\pm 45_2/90_2/\pm 45]_S$ (2.5 mm). Figures 3d and 4d show that both composites suffered severe damage after 12.87 J impact.

B. Scanning Electronic Microscopy

(a) Effect of fiber orientation

Figures 5a and 6a show the SEM of unimpacted $[\underline{+45}/\underline{0}_2]_{2S}$ and $[0/\underline{+45}/\underline{90}/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$ PEEK/C.F. From Figure 5b one can find that on the rear face of $[\underline{+45}/\underline{0}_2]_{2S}$ showed fiber breakage on 45° layer under 4.29J impact energy. The damaged area on 45° layer increased with impact energy. Result can be seen on Figures 5c and 5d.

Figure 6b shows the damage of $[0/\underline{+45}/\underline{90}/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$ is fiber breakage on 0° layers. The 0° fiber breakage on the rear face layer of the composite increased with impact energy, results are shown on Figures 6c and 6d.

(b) Effect of composite thickness

Figures 7a and 8a illustrate the structure of $[0_2/\underline{+45}/\underline{90}_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.0 mm) and $[0_2/\underline{+45}_2/\underline{90}_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.5 mm). As shown in Figures 7b and 8b, only matrix cracking occurred in $[0_2/\underline{+45}/\underline{90}_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.0 mm) and $[0_2/\underline{+45}_2/\underline{90}_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.5 mm) when they suffered 4.29 J impact energy. Fiber breakage on 0° layers occurred in both composites and $[0_2/\underline{+45}/\underline{90}_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.0 mm) more severe damage than that of $[0_2/\underline{+45}_2/\underline{90}_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.5 mm) when impact energy increased to 8.58 J. The result shows in Figures 7c and 8c. Figure 7d and 8d are the impacted zones of $[0_2/\underline{+45}/\underline{90}_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.0 mm) which show very severe damage when impact energy increased to 12.87 J.

III.2. Mechanical Properties

A. Effect of fiber orientation

Figures 9 to 11 illustrate the effect of impact energies on the mechanical properties of $[\underline{+45}/\underline{0}_2]_{2S}$ and $[0/\underline{+45}/\underline{90}/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$ PEEK/C.F. Results indicate that tensile and flexural strength of $[\underline{+45}/\underline{0}_2]_{2S}$ are higher than those of $[0/\underline{+45}/\underline{90}/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$ before impact.

When $[\underline{+45}/0_2]_{2S}$ suffered 4.29 J impact energy, since outside layer of fiber (45° layer) protect inside fiber (0° layer), 0° layers in the composite maintained undamaged and tensile strength was substantially retained. However, fiber on outside surface 0° layer in $[0/\underline{+45}/90/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$ was broken when it suffered the same energy. Hence, tensile strength of $[0/\underline{+45}/90/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$ decreased more significantly than that of $[\underline{+45}/0_2]_{2S}$. Although the effect of thickness on $[\underline{+45}/0_2]_{2S}$ caused larger delamination area than that of $[0/\underline{+45}/90/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$, the tendency of decreasing of flexural strength and modulus of $[\underline{+45}/0_2]_{2S}$ is the same as $[0/\underline{+45}/90/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$.

When impact energy increased to 8.58 J, fiber on 0° layer in $[0/\underline{+45}/90/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$ was broken and caused drastic decreasing on mechanical properties than that of $[\underline{+45}/0_2]_{2S}$. The mechanical properties of the composites decreased severely after suffered an impact energy of 12.87 J.

(b) Effect of composite thickness

Figures 12 to 14 illustrate the effect of impact energy on the mechanical properties of $[0_2/\underline{+45}/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.0 mm) and $[0_2/\underline{+45}_2/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.5 mm). Results indicate that the mechanical properties of $[0_2/\underline{+45}/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.0 mm) are higher than those of $[0_2/\underline{+45}_2/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.5 mm) before impact. The ratio of 0° layer thickness in $[0_2/\underline{+45}/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.0 mm) is higher than that of $[0_2/\underline{+45}_2/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.5 mm).

Since $[0_2/\underline{+45}/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.0 mm) has larger damaged area than that of $[0_2/\underline{+45}_2/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.5 mm) when they suffered 4.29 J impact energy, mechanical properties of $[0_2/\underline{+45}_2/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.5 mm) shows better retention than that of $[0_2/\underline{+45}/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.0 mm). When impact energy increased to 8.58 J and to 12.87 J, sever damage occurred in $[0_2/\underline{+45}/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.0 mm). Hence, its mechanical properties decreased greater than that of $[0_2/\underline{+45}_2/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.5 mm).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

- (1) From optical microscopy, $[0/\underline{+45}/90/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$ laminate shows more sever damage than that of $[\underline{+45}/0_2]_{2S}$ majorly due to

fiber breakage and matrix cracking.

- (2) From SEM , rear face of $[\underline{+45}/\underline{0}_2]_{2S}$ and $[0/\underline{+45}/90/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$ laminates showed fiber breakage under low impact energy (4.29 J). The damaged area increased with impact energy.
- (3) Laminate of $[0/\underline{+45}/90/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$ shows more sever fiber breakage and matrix cracking than that of $[\underline{+45}/\underline{0}_2]_{2S}$ when they suffered impact damage. The $[0/\underline{+45}/90/\underline{-45}]_{2S}$ showed lower tensile strength and flexural strength than that of $[\underline{+45}/\underline{0}_2]_{2S}$.
- (4) From optical microscopy, $[0_2/\underline{+45}/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.0 mm) shows more sever damage than that of $[0_2/\underline{+45}_2/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.5 mm) due to larger delamination, fiber breakage and matrix cracking. The main damage is delamination under 4.29 J impact loading.
- (5) Laminate of $[0_2/\underline{+45}_2/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.5 mm) shows less damaged area, the retention of mechanical properties is better than that of $[0_2/\underline{+45}/90_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ (2.0 mm).

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(a) unimpacted (b) 4.292 J (38.2 in-lb)

(c) 8.58 J (76.4 in-lb) (d) 12.87 J (114.6 in-lb)

Figure 1. Photomicrography (50X) of the damaged area of [0+45/0]₂ (APC-2) when it suffered various impact energies

(a) unimpacted (b) 4.292 J (38.2 in-lb)

(c) 8.58 J (76.4 in-lb) (d) 12.87 J (114.6 in-lb)

Figure 2. Photomicrography (50X) of the damaged area of [0+45/90+45]₂ (APC-2) when it suffered various impact energies

(a) unimpacted (b) 4.292 J (38.2 in-lb)

(c) 8.58 J (76.4 in-lb) (d) 12.87 J (114.6 in-lb)

Figure 3. Photomicrography (50X) of the damaged area of [0+45/90+90]₂ (APC-2) when it suffered various impact energies

(a) unimpacted

(b) 4.292 J (38.2 in-lb)

(c) 8.58 J (76.4 in-lb)

(d) 12.87 J (114.6 in-lb)

Figure 4. SEM diagram (25X) of the damaged area of [0+45/0]₂ (APC-2) when it suffered various impact energies

Figure 5. SEM diagram (25X) of the damaged area of [0,+45/90,+45]_c (APC-2) when it suffered various impact energies (a) unimpacted (b) 4.29J (38.2 in-lb) (c) 8.58 J (76.4 in-lb) (d) 12.87 J (114.6 in-lb)

Figure 6. Photomicrography (50X) of the damaged area of [0,+45/90,+45]_c (2.0 mm) (APC-2) when it suffered various impact energies (a) unimpacted (b) 4.29J (38.2 in-lb) (c) 8.58 J (76.4 in-lb) (d) 12.87 J (114.6 in-lb)

Figure 7. SEM diagram (25X) of the damaged area of [0,+45/90,+45]_c (2.0 mm) (APC-2) when it suffered various impact energies (a) unimpacted (b) 4.29J (38.2 in-lb) (c) 8.58 J (76.4 in-lb) (d) 12.87 J (114.6 in-lb)

Figure 8. SEM diagram (25X) of the damaged area of [0,+45/90,+45]_c (2.5 mm) (APC-2) when it suffered various impact energies (a) unimpacted (b) 4.29J (38.2 in-lb) (c) 8.58 J (76.4 in-lb) (d) 12.87 J (114.6 in-lb)

Figure 9. Tensile strength of [±45/0₂]_{2S} and [0/+45/90/-45]_{2S} (APC-2) composite after impact

Figure 10. Flexural strength of [±45/0₂]_{2S} and [0/+45/90/-45]_{2S} (APC-2) composite after impact

Figure 11. Flexural modulus of [±45/0₂]_{2S} and [0/+45/90/-45]_{2S} (APC-2) composite after impact

Figure 12. Tensile strength of [0₂/±45₂/90₂/±45]_S (2 mm) and [0₂/±45₂/90₂/±45]_S (2.5 mm) (APC-2) after impact

Figure 13. Flexural strength of [0₂/±45₂/90₂/±45]_S (2 mm) and [0₂/±45₂/90₂/±45]_S (2.5 mm) (APC-2) after impact

Figure 14. Flexural modulus of [0₂/±45₂/90₂/±45]_S (2 mm) and [0₂/±45₂/90₂/±45]_S (2.5 mm) (APC-2) after impact